

ISic1379

I.Sicily inscription 1379

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo S. Nicolai

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140885

1. [ἐνθάδε] κῆται [— —]
2. [— — ζ]ήσας [ἔτη]
3. [—'· τελ]εῦ [τᾶ τῆ πρὸ]
4. [— — Ἴ]αν[ουαρίων].
- 5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492993

EDCS 39101760

PHI 140885

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. *Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae*

Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0560 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)
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